

GRAMMATICAL STRUCTURE OF THE LANGUAGE. INTERPRETATION OF GRAMMATICAL CATEGORIES

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ANNOTATION: Grammar is the main part of linguistics. The purpose of this article is to illustrate some types of grammar and their usage. Moreover, it demonstrates language interpretation of grammatical categories.

KEY WORDS: grammatical construction of the language, grammatical structure of speech, morphology, syntax, categorical and non-categorical forms, phraseology, sentence, historical grammar, philosophical grammar, general grammar, comparative grammar, descriptive grammar.

INTRODUCTION

Grammar is a component of linguistics, and its relationship with other fields of linguistics is multifaceted and complex.

In the past, grammar was understood to teach the laws and rules that help us write and speak correctly. Today, the term grammar is used in two senses in linguistics. Grammar means, firstly, the grammatical construction of the language, and secondly, the science of the grammatical construction of the language. In the second sense, grammar is the science of the division of words into certain categories, the forms specific to each of them, and the grammatical construction of speech.

It is known that language serves as a tool of exchange of ideas in human society. Every language must have a certain number of grammatical devices to enable people to communicate. But words alone are not enough to form a sentence. In a sentence, words are united based on the grammatical and phonetic rules of each language and express a certain idea.

The grammatical structure of the language has its own categories and units. These are word forms, phrases and sentences.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

There are following types of grammar:

- historical grammar
- philosophical grammar
- general (universal) grammar
- comparative grammar

- descriptive grammar (descriptive)
- transformational grammar.

Historical grammar studies the development of changes in the grammatical structure of a language.

The main task of philosophical grammar is to study the communication possibilities of language and thinking, logical and grammatical categories. General grammar defines the common features and laws common to all languages, regardless of which language family they belong to.

Comparative grammar compares and contrasts the grammatical systems of languages with each other, and studies their common and special features.

Comparative grammar, in turn, is divided into comparative-historical and typological-comparative grammars. Rasmus Rask (1787-1832) "Old Icelandic and the Emergence of the Icelandic Language". Y.A. Grimm "Grammar of the German Language" (1819).

Descriptive grammar studies the current (synchronous) state of the grammatical structure of a specific language. Descriptive grammar uses formal methods to determine language units and their meaning. In descriptive grammar, meaning is not taken into account in the process of analyzing the construction of language.

Structural linguistics pays great attention to the study of the internal construction of the language, relations between the elements that make up the language system, and oppositions. Structural linguistics is a unique new trend in language learning and defining the subject of science. There are two methods of language system research: distributive analysis method and transformational analysis method.

RESEARCH AND DISCUSSION

Every language has countless sentences and these new sentences are correctly understood by the listener. Naturally, the following question arises: How does a speech listener understand new words that he has not heard before? The main reason for this is that there is an unlimited number of sentences, a certain number of elements of which appear in speech based on syntactic models. But the number of these syntactic models (nuclear sentences) is limited and in practice there can be only a few. For example: noun part - verb part.

Elementary, simple models of sentences are called core sentences in transformational grammar. Sentences based on this model are transformations of that core sentence. The main goal of transformational analysis is to study the syntactic models of a certain number of innumerable sentences in the language -

nuclear sentences. The transformational method is based on the idea that the language system consists of several sub-systems of the syntactic layer itself. One of them is the main core sentence, and the other is the transformations formed from core sentences. The process of studying the formation of transformations from core sentences is called transformational analysis.

Lexical meaning is an individual meaning, one meaning is associated with one word. Grammatical meaning is fundamentally different from lexical meaning. Like the lexical meaning, it does not reflect things and events in the external world and does not have an individual character. They are general meanings.

Although lexical and grammatical meanings are different from each other according to their characteristics, they are connected with each other in speech. One cannot happen without the other. Grammatical meaning appears in addition to lexical meaning and expresses various grammatical relationships: the relationship of one word to another, the relationship of a word to person, number, tense, etc. shows the connection to For example: house, pear, book, fox, neutron, joint. They have six lexical meanings but one grammatical meaning. Subject, in the singular, in the main agreement.

CONCLUSION

All in all, grammar, rules of a language governing the sounds, words, sentences, and other elements, as well as their combination and interpretation. The word grammar also denotes the study of these abstract features or a book presenting these rules. Grammar can be defined as the specific set of rules which helps us to arrange the words in the sentences to form a proper meaning. It can also be defined as the structure and system of a language in which it usually consists of morphology and syntaxes.

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